

Development of All-Composite Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) Pressure Vessel for Vehicle Use

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Summary

While the market for natural gas, oxygen or hydrogen storage, e.g. for the use in natural gas powered vehicles (NGV) is continuously growing, metallic (CNG1) and hoop wrapped metallic pressure vessels (CNG2) are more and more substituted by fully wrapped metal liner (CNG3) and all-composite (CNG4) pressure vessels which bring weight savings of up to 75%. In the CNG4 type vessel the metallic liner is replaced by a non-load carrying thermoplastic liner. Advantages and disadvantages of CNG3 and CNG4 Types are mentioned, especially the feasibility for storage of different media. The design and different burst pressures are shown followed by manufacturing technique and filament winding theory underlined by examples taken from COMATs actual manufacturing, development and testing of fiber reinforced pressure vessels.

Introduction

Initially Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) pressure vessels were restricted to the use of metallic materials (CNG1), which limited their usage basically due to the high weight. With the successful development of Composite Materials, hoop wrapped metallic pressure vessels (CNG2) were introduced to the market followed by fully wrapped metallic pressure vessels (CNG3). The latest stage of development is the all-composite pressure vessel (CNG4).

Applications for Composite CNG pressure vessels are mainly in automotive industry, for example as storage vessel for cars, trucks and busses.

Fig. 1 Application for Composite CNG Pressure vessel in busses /ref7/

The weight saving that can be reached, with composite overwrap, compared to metal vessels, is shown in the following diagram.

$$L_g = \frac{\text{operational pressure} * \text{vessel volume}}{\text{mass of the vessel}}$$

Fig. 2 Comparison of different pressure vessel types (ref. 1)

Replacing the metal liner by a non-load carrying thermoplastic liner, the weight saving potential of an all-composite pressure vessel in comparison to a GFRP hoop reinforced aluminum vessel is expected to be approximately 50% and to a full steel vessel 75%.

Comparing fully wrapped aluminum pressure vessel (CNG3) with all-composite pressure vessels (CNG4), advantages and disadvantages for both types of pressure vessels can be detected. The costs for liner manufacturing, including end connections are similar for both types of pressure vessels. Due to the lower liner weight, the total weight of a CNG4 pressure vessel is lower than a CNG3 pressure vessel therefore the gas-permeability rate of plastic liner might be little higher than for aluminum liner but is still low enough for CNG application. High modulus carbon fiber need to be used for reinforcement of CNG3 due to the low fatigue strength of aluminum. CNG4 pressure vessels can be reinforced with all different types of fiber, even glass and aramid fiber can be used as plastic liner have high fatigue strength and no special fiber needs to be used. CNG4 vessels have to be handled and cured with machinery equipment that assure no deformation of the plastic liner during manufacturing. Due to the lower temperature resistance of standard Thermoplasts compared to Aluminum, deformation of the liner during manufacturing is avoided by pressurizing the thermoplastic liner during winding and curing.

An overview of the comparison is shown in Table 1. The decision, which type of pressure vessel shall be used depends on the application and the customer needs. For both types of pressure vessels approvals by authorities have been made and both types of pressure vessels are successful on the market. COMAT also manufactures or provides know-how for manufacturing both types of pressure vessels, CNG3 and CNG4 pressure vessels, depending on customer needs.

Type of Pressure Vessel	CNG3	CNG4
Handling during Manufacturing	++	+
Liner Permeability Rate	++	+
Cycling Stability	+	++
Liner Costs	++	++
Fiber Costs	+	++
Total Costs	+	++
Total Weight	+	++
Safety	++	++
Approval by Authorities	++	++
Market Acceptance	++	++

Table 1: Comparison between fully wrapped CNG3 (aluminum Liner) and CNG4 (plastic Liner) pressure vessel

Design

The pressure vessel design generally starts with the liner and laminate design. When the vessel is reinforced by filament winding over a liner, in more than one direction, the wall is no longer symmetric and first ply failure does not necessarily mean total failure of the vessel.

The lay-up of the composite overwrap is applied first by winding helical layers at an angle of $\pm\omega$ in the cylindrical section. These helical windings are continued over the heads with an angle that varies with position on the dome. The helical angle in the cylindrical section is determined by the design of the dome and the diameter of the dome end fittings relative to the diameter of the cylinder. Typical values of the helical angle can vary between 10° and 35° . Additional hoop windings are then wound over the cylindrical section. It is a typical way to design the cylinder lay-up as an alternation of hoop and helical plies reducing the voids in the helical laminate. The domes are designed to be stronger to force the ultimate rupture of the tank to take place in the cylindrical section.

A wrapped shell is called isotensoidal shell if any of its fibers is strained by equal tension. Predicting geodesic fiber paths in a filament wound pressure vessel, constant fiber tensions can be guaranteed which meets the requirements of the manufacturing process to avoid fiber slip off. This condition is known as the Clairaut condition $r \sin \omega = const. = r_p$

The required burst pressure for all-composite pressure vessels with 200 bar working pressure, is given in Table 2:

Fiber-Material	Burst Pressure CNG3	Burst Pressure CNG4
Glass	700 bar	730 bar
Aramid	600 bar	620 bar
Carbon	470 bar	470 bar

Table 2: Required burst pressure for composite pressure vessel with 200bar working pressure (ref. 3)

According to the described design, COMAT FilaWin® CNG pressure vessels were manufactured and tested.

Manufacturing

The concept of high-speed, precise laydown of continuous reinforcement in prescribed patterns is the basis of the filament winding method. It is a process by which continuous resin-impregnated reinforcements in the form of rovings or tows are wound over a rotating mandrel. In case of filament winding CNG3 and CNG4 pressure vessel, the mandrel is shaped cylindrical with spherical domes. The reinforcement is wrapped in adjacent bands or in repeating bands that are stepped the width of the band and that eventually cover the mandrel surface. The technique can vary winding tension, winding angle, or resin content in each layer of reinforcement until the desired thickness and resin content of composite is achieved with the required direction of composite strength.

Fig. 3 Winding Pattern (ref.7)

Prior to the design phase of a composite structure, decisions must be made in terms of fabrication and materials that will impact the cost and producibility of the component. With the size, shape, and material selected, the choice of winding patterns can be made. The two basic winding patterns are hoop and helical winding.

Hoop patterns are also known as girth, 90-degree, or circumferential winding. Strictly speaking, hoop winding is a high-angle helical winding that approaches an angle of 90 degrees. Each full rotation of the mandrel advances the band delivery one full band width. In helical winding, the mandrel rotates more or less continuously while the fiber feed carriage traverses back and forth at a speed regulated to generate the desired helical angle. The normal winding pattern provides a multicircuit helix. After the first circuit, the applied fibers are not adjacent, and additional circuits must be traversed before the pattern begins to lay adjacent to previous windings. The helical pattern is characterized by fiber crossovers at periodically appearing locations along the mandrel's length. A layer is made up of a two-ply balanced laminate. The mandrel revolutions per circuit vary with the winding angle, the band width and the overall length of the vessel. Both winding patterns, hoop and helical, are used for manufacturing composite pressure vessels.

Fig. 4 Winding dome section of pressure vessel

The following pictures show different types of FilaWin® pressure vessels manufactured by COMAT.

Fig. 5 FilaWin® Hoop wrapped metallic cylinder for NGV and Hydrogen Storage

Fig. 6 FilaWin[®] 50l Carbon fiber reinforced CNG pressure vessels

Fig. 7 FilaWin[®] 110l Glass Fiber reinforced CNG pressure vessel

Testing

Various tests had been passed in order to approve the performance of FilaWin[®] composite pressure vessels. The objective of mechanical testing of an engineering material is to provide data necessary for analysis, design and fabrication of structural components using the material. The testing of composite materials offers unique challenges because of the special characteristics of composites. Techniques for fabricating ring - type test specimens are outlined in ASTM. The standard ring for example is 146 mm (5.75 inches) inside diameter, 6.35 mm (0.25 inch) wide, and either 1.52 mm (0.60 inch) or 3.18 mm (0.125 inch) thick. Ring specimens were simple to prepare because the specimen consists of only circumferentially wound fibers. The ring had been wound on a cylindrical mandrel using mandrel, and cured without special compaction devices. Thus, the specimen is typical of many unidirectional filament wound laminates. It is widely used for characterizing filament wound laminates.

Furthermore interlaminar shear strength has been measured as an important value for characterization of the raw material used. Besides ensuring that the incoming materials meets the required specifications and are consistent from lot to lot, all tests serve to substantiate the use of these materials throughout their shelf life. Before winding several liner test have been passed as dimensional check and leak test.

After winding all cylinder have been hydrostatically tested at 1.5 times working pressure. Therefore the hydrostatic pressure in the cylinder has been increased gradually and regularly until the test pressure has been reached. The cylinder test pressure had been held for at least 30 seconds to ascertain that there is no tendency for the pressure to decrease and that tightness is guaranteed.

In addition hydrostatic and dynamic burst pressure tests have been passed.

The rate of pressurization did not exceed 14 bar per second (200 psi/second) and there had been at least a 5 second hold at the minimum design burst pressure before increasing the pressure to rupture the vessel.

Finally, the finite element stress analysis had been verified by applying strain gages at different positions of the pressure vessel as shown in Figure 8.

Fig.8 Verification of stress analysis by strain test of FilaWin[®] all-composite pressure vessel

Results and Conclusion

The developed CNG Composite pressure vessels performed very well. The following table gives a summary of the burst pressure test results as well as the cycle test results. All FilaWin[®] pressure vessels fulfilled the required tests in accordance to the standards.

Fiber	Total Weight	Burst Pressure
Glass	53 kg	750 bar
Carbon	20 kg	745 bar

Table 3: Burst pressure test results for FilaWin[®] CNG4 /501

Fiber	Total Weight	No. of Cycles	Pressure Range	Burst Pressure after Cycling
Glass	53 kg	15.000	20-260 bar	755 bar
Carbon	20 kg	20.000	20-200 bar	810 bar

Table 4: Cycle pressure test results for FilaWin[®] CNG4 /501

Due to the very positive results, COMAT keeps on developing customized pressure vessels for natural gas, oxygen or hydrogen storage. Aluminum lined as well as plastic lined pressure vessels have future markets and are both part of the products and know-how that is available to our customers. Also non cylindrical pressure vessels become more and more interesting for mobile application and are part of development for the near future.

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